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Good practice guide

Use of the prototype sources for the ultraviolet spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the ultraviolet spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Ultraviolet (UV) radiation: Optical radiation for which the wavelengths are shorter than those for visible radiation. For UV radiation, the range between 100 nm and 400 nm is commonly subdivided into:

UV-A: 315 nm to 400 nm,

UV-B: 280 nm to 315 nm, and

UV-C: 100 nm to 280 nm.

(see 17-21-008 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

According to ISO 20473:2007, ultraviolet (UV) radiation includes the UV-A and UV-B spectral ranges, i.e., 280 nm to 380 nm. The UV-C spectral range is divided into vacuum ultraviolet (VUV; 100 nm to 190 nm) and deep ultraviolet (DUV; 190 nm to 280 nm). Also 1 nm to 100 nm spectral range is defined as extreme ultraviolet (EUV).

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Source based on UV LED and UV phosphors

3.1. Design description

The new UV standard source depicted in Figure 1 has been designed for wavelength region from 250 nm to 450 nm. The source consists of a UVC LED matrix emitting radiation at the wavelength of 277 nm, and a UVA + UVB phosphor disk that absorbs a big part of the LED radiation and re-emits it at longer wavelengths covering UV-A and UV-B regions. The LED produces approximately 200 mW of radiation and consumes approximately 17 W of electrical power. The LED matrix is thus attached on an air-cooled heatsink to get rid of the excess heat. A UV coated Ø75 mm plano-convex lens has been added to the design to collect intensity. The focal length of the lens is 90 mm, and it has been set off-focus, to produce a blurred beam profile instead of a focused image to maintain spatial uniformity.

The intensity at the measurement distance of 500 mm is close to a 1 kW incandescent halogen lamp at 500 mm distance as can be seen in Figure 2. Figure 3 presents the key components of the light source, an LED matrix of 3 x 3 LEDs and a phosphor disk, containing UV emitting phosphor forming a layer on top of a quartz disk.

Figure 1: UV light source based on a UV-C LED matrix and a phosphor component covering UV-A and UV-B regions. Visible are the aluminium heat sink stabilising the temperature of the LED and the phosphor component, and the outermost lens condensing radiation.

Figure 2: Spectral irradiance of the new source at the distance of 500 mm (black solid line) and spectral irradiance of a 1 kW incandescent halogen lamp (green dashed line) for comparison. The lowest of the three peaks at the wavelength of 277 nm is produced by the LED matrix. The emission at higher wavelengths including the three peaks at the wavelengths near 310 nm, 340 nm and 375 nm are produced by the phosphor disk.

Figure 3: Components of the UV light source, (a) the LED matrix, and (b) three prototype pieces of the phosphor disk.

3.2. Specifications

Figure 4 presents the optical arrangement of the source built inside an optical tube. Distance between the LED matrix and the phosphor disk is $d_{\text{Phos}} = 22.9$ mm. Distance between the phosphor disk and the lens is $d_{\text{Lens}} = 64.0$ mm. The distance from the lens to the outermost surface of the tube is $d_{\text{Cap}} = 47.3$ mm.

The reference plane for distance measurements is the outermost surface of the tube with its protecting cap closed. Measurement distance from this reference plane is $d_{\text{Meas}} = 500.0$ mm.

Figure 4: Optical arrangement of the source. For dimensions, see text.

The LED matrix is operated with current of 1.000 A. Leads have banana plugs. The voltage across the lamp rises upto 17.3 V.

The fan is operated with a voltage source providing 5 V via banana plugs. Inside the heat sink, there is a 10 k Ω NTC thermistor that is read with a multimeter. There is an adapter providing banana plugs for connection.

The output spectrum is according to Figure 2. The total irradiance in the measurement plane is ~517 mW m⁻² integrated over wavelength. The irradiance of the LED peak is 47 mW m⁻² integrated over the wavelength range from 250 nm to 295 nm. The corresponding irradiance over the phosphor region between 296 nm and 450 nm is 470 mW m⁻².

3.3. Safety and handling instructions

The light source produces UV radiation. The amount is not high but may be harmful to eyes if stared at. Use of safety glasses is recommended.

The UV radiation generates tiny amounts of ozone.

3.4. Operating conditions

Environment

The light source has been designed and tested to be used in ordinary laboratory conditions, temperature preferably 23 °C.

Fan cooling

The LED matrix generates about 17 W of power. With the fan on, the temperature of the heat sink and the LED matrix rises to 29 °C, 6 °C above the environmental temperature. Without fan (not recommended) the temperature rises to above 35 °C. The fan is operated with a 5 V power supply.

Electrical parameters

The LED matrix is operated with 1.000 A DC current. Voltage over the lamp is monitored and compared to earlier values. The voltage level is approximately 17.3 V.

Alignment and reference plane

The measuring device should be positioned 500.0 mm from the reference plane (front plate), on an optical axis defined by a mirror placed in contact with the front plate and a laser reflected from the mirror, and the centre of the front plate marked with an X.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed. The intensity gradually decays. Thus, a record is kept on the lamp burn hours, including voltage across the lamp in the beginning and at the end.

3.5. Limitations

3.5.1. Ageing

The intensity of the lamp decays gradually as can be seen in Figure 5. Intensity integrated over the LED peak region, from 250 nm to 295 nm, drops by 0.11 %/h. Corresponding decay in the phosphor region, integrated from 296 nm to 450 nm is 0.03 %/h.

Figure 5: Ageing of the lamp. Blue circles denote irradiance values integrated over the full spectral range from 250 nm to 450 nm. Orange crosses are irradiance integrated over the LED peak, and green triangles are irradiances integrated over the phosphor region.

3.5.2. Spatial uniformity

Figure 6: Spatial uniformity of the irradiance field measured at the distance of 500 mm. (a) Measurement wavelength 280 nm corresponding to the LED peak, and (b) 334 nm corresponding to the phosphor region.

The lens used to collect radiation causes significant non-uniformity to the irradiance field as can be seen in Figure 6. The non-uniformity is slightly different for the LED peak and the phosphor region of the spectrum, because the sources appear at different locations.

Figure 7 shows a magnified figure over a small region in the centre of the measurement plane. Figure 8 shows correction factors that may be taken into account when comparing measurement devices with varied input aperture sizes.

Figure 7: Magnified figure of the spatial uniformity over a region ± 15 mm in X- and Y-directions. Measurement has been carried out with a 3 mm aperture.

Figure 8: Irradiance masked through different sizes of measurement apertures. Figures have been obtained by integrating the data of Figure 7 over varied circular areas.

3.5.3. Size of source and distance dependence.

The light from the source is condensed with a lens having 75 mm diameter. When measuring, this whole area should be visible and if blocked for dark signal measurement, the whole area should be blocked.

The lens causes the distance behaviour to deviate significantly from inverse square law. Thus, distance corrections and uncertainties cannot be calculated with inverse square law.

4. Source based on UV LEDs

4.1. Design description

The tuneable broadband UV LED source is designed and established having 250 nm to 405 nm wavelength range and higher than 1 mW m⁻² at each wavelength. The source consists of 79 LEDs, arranged in fourteen spectral groups, each group containing LEDs with a different peak wavelength. The model numbers and specifications of the LEDs used in the designed source are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: LED components of the tuneable broadband UV LED source.

	Model No	WL (nm)	LED Quantity	Optical PWR (mW)	Technology	O/P Optics
UVC	HYE35P40F250AG-P1	255	5	90	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVC	HYE35P30F260AG-P1	265	6	60	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVC	HYE35P20F270AG-P1	275	11	35	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVB	XBT-3535-285 nm	285	6	70	AlGaIn	Borosilicate glass
UVB	HYE35P20F290AG-P1	295	5	70	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVB	HYE35P20F310AG-P1	310	13	30	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	HYE35P20F325AG-P1	325	13	90	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	HYE35P20F340AG-P1	340	11	40	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	LN-SMD3838UVB-P3	350	4	100	AlGaIn	Quartz glass
UVA	GT-3535P365-1CC0-GH45M	365	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	RZX-S3838-375NM-3W-N60	375	1	1000	AlGaIn	Quartz lens
UVA	GT-3535P380-1CC0-GH45M	385	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	GT-3535P395-1CC0-GH45M	395	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	GT-3535P400-1CC0-GH45M	405	1	1000	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens

The LEDs were positioned on a circular PCB in the configuration shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 in order to achieve uniform irradiation.

Figure 9: Schematic layout of the 79 UV LEDs, illustrating the placement and wavelength classification of the LEDs within the circular PCB.

Figure 10: Picture of the LEDs on the PCB.

Multi-channel current driver provides current the 14 LED groups. Each current channel can be set a current value responding to relating LED group. The current values can be set the maximum or less any other current

The spectrum given in Figure 13 shows multiple low-intensity peaks in the region from 260 nm to 350 nm, representing the combined emission of several UV LED groups with closely spaced wavelengths. The two strong maxima around ~365 nm and ~395 nm indicate that the LED types at these wavelengths contribute the dominant radiant power. The low-intensity peaks between 260 nm and 350 nm, where the smallest peaks are below approximately $0.03 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$. The two dominant emission bands occur near ~365 nm and ~395 nm, with the maximum peak reaching about $0.27 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$.

Figure 13: (a) Spectral irradiance of the source at a distance of 500 mm. (b) Output of the source.

The source exhibits very stable spectral output over the UV range after the initial warm-up period. In the region from 250 nm to 300 nm, the stability after 30 minutes remains within $\pm 1 \%$, while in the 300–405 nm range the variation is further reduced to below $\pm 0.5 \%$ is shown in Figure 14. After one hour of operation, the stability curve shows an additional improvement, indicating that the system reaches a steady thermal and electrical equilibrium.

Figure 14: Stability of the source.

4.3. Safety and handling instructions

- Do not move when the source is switched on.
- Apply the current to the LEDs after TEC is active.
- Never look directly at the emitting surface while the source is operating.
- Always wear appropriate UV-blocking protective eyewear and laboratory gloves.
- Avoid exposing skin directly to the UV beam. Use shielding whenever possible.
- Do not block airflow around measurement area.
- Keep the device away from water, solvents, and corrosive chemicals.

4.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling

Since the large number of LEDs generates a significant thermal load on the 10 cm-diameter PCB, temperature monitoring is performed not only via the temperature sensor located behind the TEC cold plate but also by an additional sensor placed at the centre of the PCB. Because the target temperature on the PCB is 25 °C, the LED board can be maintained at this level when the TEC is fixed at 18 °C. To ensure stable source irradiance, the TEC temperature must remain constant at 18 °C so that the PCB temperature, as monitored by the onboard sensor, stays close to 25 °C.

Electrical parameters

The source must be switched on only when the TEC is active. The external DC power supply must provide 12 V and 15 A to drive the multi-channel current driver. Using the user interface software, the operator must set the driving current for the LEDs across 14 channels, ensuring that the current for each channel remains below the maximum value indicated as “MAX:” in the interface.

Alignment and reference plane

The sensor should be positioned such that its centre aligns with the centre of the PCB. A distance of 500 mm is recommended for the measurements.

Spatial homogeneity

The physical configuration, where multiple LEDs of various wavelengths are positioned within a 10 cm circular PCB results in a broad area of emission. Consequently, the spatial homogeneity cannot be expected to be as ideal as that of a point source. Nevertheless, measurements have not been conducted to characterise this parameter.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed.

4.5. Limitations

The main limitations of the source in comparison with a standard QTH lamp are

- Irradiance spatial homogeneity
- Spectral lateral homogeneity

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